

Elections in the Canton of Bern 2010–2018

Tobias Kindler, 7 February 2024

From 2010 until 2022 (and more or less confirmed in the 2022 elections) the right conservative parties – the Swiss people’s party (SVP), the Conservative Democratic Party of Switzerland (BDP), the Liberals (FDP), and the Federal Democratic Union of Switzerland (EDU) – held the majority of the 160 seats in the cantonal parliament in the canton of Bern (see Figure 1). While there were some shifts and changes within the left-center-right blocks, there was little variation across these three blocks over the three legislative periods (Canton Bern, 2022).

As can be seen in Figure 2, the situation was the opposite in the cantonal government. From 2010 until 2016, the Social Democratic Party (SP) and the Green Party held four of the seven seats in the government. This rather untypical situation was called “cohabitation”, referring to the parliament being dominated by conservative-right forces, while the government has a left-green majority. This changed in 2016, when two of the three SP members of the government resigned in the middle of their term for personal and professional reasons. In their election campaign, the Swiss People’s Party (SVP) promised tax reductions and stronger austerity programs. They were successful: While the social democrats were able to hold one of the two vacant seats, the other was won by SVP. Since this election, the conservative-right parties, SVP, FDP, BDP, hold a majority of seats both in the parliament and in the government (Bühlmann & Schubiger, 2024).

With this change, the new elected SVP member of the government, Pierre Alain Schnegg, became the new head of the department of health, social welfare and integration, which before was in the hands of the social democrats since 1976. As promised in his election campaign, Schnegg did not lose much time and started to cut back the social sector, among them social welfare assistance (Bühlmann & Schubiger, 2024).

Figure 1. Left = AL, GaP, Grüne, PSA, SP. Center = CVP, EVP GLP. Right = SVP, BDP, FDP, EDU. Source: Canton Bern, 2022

Figure 2. Source: Bühlmann & Schubiger, 2024

References

Bühlmann, Marc; Schubiger, Maximilian 2024. Ausgewählte Beiträge zur Schweizer Politik: Dossier: Kantonale Wahlen - Bern, 2010 - 2018. Bern: Année Politique Suisse, Institut für Politikwissenschaft, Universität Bern. www.anneepolitique.swiss. Date of access: 7 February 2024

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